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Governance, Interoperability, Guidance: a People Centred Approach to Cross-sector Data Sharing Infrastructure

This report draws on inputs from
the Data Sharing Working Group

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Executive summary and recommendations

The UK lacks a clear, authoritative governance framework for cross-sector data sharing. Fragmented responsibilities, unclear hierarchies and gaps in standards and guidance create friction, cost, and risk. In this vacuum, a small number of large technology firms could define de facto rules and infrastructure in ways that entrench dependency and anti-competitive outcomes. Discussions within the Data Sharing Working Group (DSWG) highlight persistent socio-technical barriers, including limited semantic, legal, and governance interoperability and incomplete guidance resulting in disparate data stewardship practices. Emerging sector-based Data Sharing Infrastructures (DSIs) in energy and water show excellent progress but also reveal challenges in scaling use case driven approaches and sector-based frameworks without cross-sector alignment. This report proposes a hybrid governance model combining a government backed central coordinating authority with a cross-sector Data Sharing Infrastructure Forum to surface emerging best practice, develop shared frameworks, and build trusted, interoperable data sharing infrastructure. Clear guidance, licensing frameworks, and shared ontological approaches are essential to underpin security, trust, and pro-competitive innovation across the UK's digital ecosystem.

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The Data Sharing Working Group and the scope of this report

The Data Sharing Working Group (DSWG) was established in 2022 by Sarah Hayes on a voluntary basis. It has grown to a membership of around 200 data sharing practitioners across industry, academia and government. Over 2025-26 the DSWG met to discuss emerging best practice in the areas of: governance, legal and regulatory, data interoperability, security and trust as components of data sharing infrastructure set out in the earlier DSWG reports^{1,2}. In addition, NESO and Stream are developing data sharing infrastructures for the energy and water sectors and offered valuable insights into the connecting of sector-based data sharing infrastructures. The DSWG discuss all types of data sharing; open data, smart data (the secure sharing of customer data³) and system data including non-personal data such as asset data. The focus of this report is data sharing infrastructure primarily in the sectors and domains covered by the DSWG: advanced manufacturing, agrifood, automotive, built environment, energy, geospatial, natural environment and climate, telecoms, transport and water. Sector based data sharing infrastructures may have different types of data in and out of scope. For example, energy data sharing infrastructure does not currently include consumer data but has plans to, through collaboration with the consumer consent service (CCS) being developed by RECCo. Smart energy data is included in the Smart Data Strategy⁴. Stream (Water data sharing infrastructure) can include consumer data if a use case justifies it. Smart water data is not currently included in the Smart Data Strategy.

This report sets out key insights and recommendations with respect to cross-sector data sharing emerging from discussions over December 2025 to March 2026 and is produced with the support of the Birmingham Energy Institute at the University of Birmingham as part of the second phase of the Diatomic project⁵.

References

1 [CPC00769_Cross-sector-UK-Data-Sharing-Infrastructure.pdf](#)

2 [Data Sharing Working Group Annual Report 2024-2025 – Digital Twin Hub](#)

3 [Smart Data Strategy - GOV.UK](#)

4 *Ibid*

5 <https://cp.catapult.org.uk/project/diatomic/>

The DSWG discussions

Figure 1

Components of Data Sharing Infrastructure diagram⁶.

Discussions in the DSWG framed across the components of Data Sharing Infrastructure (DSI) set out in the diagram above and covering both public and private sector data have revealed the following **persistent problems and barriers** to realising the value from data sharing:

- Current digital systems are fragmented, siloed, and lack interoperability, which aligns with findings from Li et al (2025)⁷ and the perspective of Project CONCRETE⁸.
- Technical capability exists to share data, but social and organisational barriers remain the main blockers. Socio-cultural change is the real barrier. Adoption challenges persist. Coordination and collaboration are hard, and voluntary effort is not enough, it needs to be paid for and factored into Data Sharing Infrastructure Initiatives.
- Multiple Data Sharing Infrastructure Initiatives (DSII) are emerging and whilst this marks significant progress in data sharing, it is becoming harder to connect up and share data across sectors, because each DSI has its own approach to governance and interoperability.
- This means data is not shared across different sectors (e.g. energy-water-transport-agriculture) and is not yet widely used to inform long-term decisions.
- The result is missed opportunities for deriving value and driving economic growth.

Without a common thread of interoperability across data sharing infrastructure initiatives, it becomes harder to share data across sectors due to:

- **Lack of semantic interoperability.** Semantic interoperability is the ability for data from one system to be understood unambiguously by another. It enables machine to machine communication. Without a foundation data model also referred to as a top-level ontology, we have no formal approach to agreeing what terms mean. Today, sectors and organisations often translate between bespoke data models, which is inefficient and prevents scaling. The long-term direction is towards adopting a shared foundation data model across sectors.
- **Lack of legal interoperability.** Legal interoperability is about ensuring that organisations operating under different legal frameworks, policies and strategies are able to work together⁹. DSIs have bespoke data sharing agreements and approaches to licensing. This can make it time-consuming and costly to share data across DSIs and sector-based DSIs because significant legal input may be required to understand and overcome the differences. This negatively impacts security and trust.
- **Lack of governance interoperability.** There is no guiding hand to initiate cross-sector data sharing. When data needs to be shared across sectors it is not clear which sector's rules should prevail. There is a need for a clear set of rules, agreed by users to enable high quality information to be rapidly deployed across different

References

⁶ Digital Twin Hub, Data Sharing Working Group CC-BY-SA 4.0.

⁷ Li, F., et al.: Do we need a data sharing infrastructure for the energy sector? IET Smart Grid. e12196 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1049/stg2.12196>

⁸ Project CONCRETE, under development in the Ministry of Defence (unclassified), is developing an open, user-centric, sector-agnostic blueprint for secure digital collaboration and interoperability in support of minimal national digital standards.

⁹ [3. Interoperability layers | Interoperable Europe Portal](#)

The DSWG discussions continued

markets. Addressing this requires the configuration of steering groups, oversight committees, advisory groups and working groups as recommended by Icebreaker One¹⁰. Beyond this, there is a need for governance of semantic interoperability approaches and to enforce rules where necessary. There is a lack of governance on technical design principles for DSIs which makes it difficult to scale beyond a use case-based approach because there is not enough coordination or sharing of learned knowledge.

‘The discussions emphasised the lack of clear, practical guidance that disseminates best practice.’

There is consensus that the challenges are primarily socio-technical as the technical interoperability elements (network, syntactic and operation of hardware systems) are deemed to be addressable through international standards. The socio-technical challenges are chiefly social in nature as they require coordination and consensus. People-centred approaches of agreeing priorities, standards and solutions are the key enablers of the types of interoperability which are currently missing from data sharing infrastructure.

The discussions emphasised the **lack of clear, practical guidance** that disseminates best practice. As a result, many organisations and local authorities lack consistent guidance on information management and data sharing, highlighting the need for framework approaches, reusable templates where appropriate and licensing guidelines. Whilst the implementation of data sharing may be use-case and place-based, there would be benefit from having national level guidance so that local organisations, such as local authorities and regional organisations, don't have to reinvent the wheel with respect to data sharing agreements, licensing and security and trust arrangements. It was also noted that where guidance exists, it can be difficult to navigate, inconsistent and provide limited practical support. In particular participants noted the lack of clear data stewardship guidance providing advice on ontologies and understanding information requirements.

Interoperability is hard to achieve, and guidance is patchy because governance is the key missing ingredient. Discussions in the DSWG covered both:

- **Organisational governance** refers to the structures that enable decision-making, encompassing legislation and regulation, sector-specific regulatory frameworks, industry guidance, and internal governance structures such as steering groups and programme boards. Data sharing initiatives would ideally comply with top-level strategic governance while also establishing their own internal governance to manage delivery, accountability, and risk.
- **Data governance** refers to the rules, principles, and responsibilities for managing, sharing, accessing, and using data. This includes data standards, roles and responsibilities, data quality and stewardship, access controls and sensitivity classifications, and data sharing agreements and liability frameworks.

Both organisational and data governance are currently underdeveloped across sectors:

- **Organisational governance** suffers from the absence of a central governance body, with voluntary collaboration lacking formal accountability. Insufficient funding and incentives compound weak cross-sector coordination and a lack of strategic vision. There is a lack of coordinated leadership and whilst many different data sharing and information management communities proliferate; they lack a people-centred focal point and as a result there is little collaboration and coordination across public and private sectors.
- Compounding this is the growing imbalance of power in the digital ecosystem. Large technology firms are moving rapidly to structure, clean, and store data in ways optimised for their own AI models and platforms. This risks a patchwork of incompatible data ecosystems each aligned to a big tech vendor. Without a public-interest governance framework, these proprietary approaches could risk becoming the default standards, effectively shaping access conditions, market dynamics, and innovation pathways without the degree of openness and extensibility required to facilitate seamless and secure data sharing across public and private data. This concentration of capability represents a significant long-term risk to the UK's ability to steward its own data assets.

References

[10 Governance \(for data sharing Schemes\) – Icebreaker One](#)

The DSWG discussions continued

– At the operational level, **data governance** remains underdeveloped. The lack of an agreed foundation data model or top-level ontology hinders efforts to use and improve existing standards to allow cross-sector data sharing, as semantic interoperability is limited. The lack of clear rules and authoritative guidance on good information practices (covering for example data quality and access controls) means organisations must incur additional costs to make their data shareable. This is a cost repeated across organisations rather than shared and minimised.

Skills and culture also pose significant barriers through limited data sharing literacy and a limited shared culture of responsible data sharing. Many organisations lack the confidence or literacy to navigate complex governance requirements and to assess the risks and benefits of sharing data. A common language for describing data, its risks, and its value does not exist. Without a shared cultural foundation, trust is limited and data sharing initiatives can struggle to gain traction, regardless of technical readiness.

Crucially, there is insufficient UK-wide articulation of what a data sharing infrastructure is, what good looks like, and how organisations should approach data stewardship and assess the risks and benefits of data sharing.

In short, there is a lack of interoperability, guidance and governance and the key enabler is getting the governance right. Governance, interoperability and guidance are all part of DSI and if they are not in place there are additional risks:

- Security becomes a bigger problem. Cross-sector integration improves insights (e.g. for net zero and climate resilience) but also increases cyber and operational risk.
- The rise of data for AI creates anti-competitive risk from big tech. Big tech solutions won't solve interoperability issues because they will create proprietary solutions to generate profit rather than open, adoptable solutions.

This is a **people-centric problem** which demands **people-centric solutions** enabling people to come together to work through and **share best practice approaches** to sharing data securely.

Figure 2

Examples of best practice:
The JLR approach to digital trust.

Emerging DSIs in Energy and Water

NESO is developing data sharing infrastructure for the energy sector and Stream is developing data sharing infrastructure for the water sector. Annex 1 sets out points of alignment across energy and water data sharing infrastructures. Full information about each respective data sharing infrastructure can be found on the NESO¹¹ and Stream¹² websites. The table below shows an overview.

	Energy DSI	Stream
The vision for the data sharing infrastructure	The Data Sharing Infrastructure (DSI) is a socio-technical solution that makes it easier for the energy sector to share data and models in a scalable, secure, and resilient way by bringing together common processes, governance, and technology. As publicly-owned digital infrastructure, it plays a crucial role in the sector's digitalisation and enabling clean power by 2030.	The vision is to unlock the potential of water data to benefit customers, society, and the environment. Stream was established through a collaboration between UK water companies, supported by industry and civil society partners.
Definition of data sharing infrastructure (what is included)	Initially referred to as the "digital spine", the terminology evolved to "Data Sharing Infrastructure" to better reflect its purpose: providing the foundational publicly-owned digital infrastructure for secure, trusted data exchange across the sector.	Broader than water industry to include all water sector and stakeholders that interact with the natural water environment. Uses four pillars to define DSI: Ecosystem = people (data publishers and consumers) Use cases = datasets = why and what Operations = processes, risk assessment Technology = means for sharing Governance around everything with value at the heart.

References

- ¹¹ [Data Sharing Infrastructure \(DSI\) | National Energy System Operator](#)
¹² [Stream - Portal](#)

Emerging DSIs in Energy and Water

continued

	Energy DSI	Stream
Scope	<p>The DSI focuses on shared data, as defined in the Open Data Institute's Data Spectrum. It is designed for any energy sector participant, from regulated networks and system users to SMEs and researchers. It will enable connectivity for many-to-many relationships and with time frequent or even live data exchanges through APIs and streaming integration patterns. The DSI provides secure data sharing mechanisms and incorporates existing data models and protocols.</p>	<p>Covers open and shared data sharing (related to sensitivity of data) and uses ODI data spectrum defining open and shared.</p> <p>Started with water industry scheme – 16 GB water companies as publishers of water data and expanded to water sector.</p> <p>Water Industry – the businesses, operations, and infrastructure involved in the delivery and management of water and wastewater services</p> <p>Water Sector = “all organisations and activities impacting on or interacting with the water system” A broader concept encompassing all activities, stakeholders, and systems that manage and derive value from water resources within a territory’s socio-economic and environmental context.</p> <p>Includes consumer data – if a use case justifies it being shared – e.g. PSR, smart meter data.</p> <p>Citizen Science scheme – this is work in progress and intends to use the same DSI the water industry scheme relies upon to enable use of participatory data to be aggregated and to be consumed, by individuals to big organisations. Citizen science data relating to water covers water quality as well as ecological data (although note: it will be careful not to duplicate other trusted sources of ecological data).</p>

This report provides no analysis of the different approaches to developing sector data sharing infrastructures but instead focuses on how the energy DSI and water DSI might consider cross-sector data sharing. This report does not represent the formal position of NESO and Stream.

Both sectors share similar aims to achieve data sharing infrastructure for their sector but differ in implementation due to regulatory structures, funding models, and sector maturity. The energy and water DSIs do indeed have different histories,

Emerging DSIs in Energy and Water

continued

regulatory drivers, and operational contexts, so their DSIs need not be identical but ultimately, they will need to be interoperable. Interoperability depends on aligned principles rather than identical architectures.

There are many highly valuable cross-sector use cases, and a shared use case is viewed as essential to test interoperability between water and energy DSIs. In approaching initial use cases, the aim is to understand where there is **equivalence between the DSIs** so that for example, if an organisation is accredited in one DSI, it can also gain entry to the other DSI. This could be similar to proving identity once for multiple government services.

The energy DSI and Stream have both arisen through stakeholder need, whether that has been articulated more strongly by the regulator or the regulated, and have had to set out their own approach to developing DSI where no clear blueprint for complex sectors like energy and water exists. There is currently no national authority providing unified design principles for DSIs across sectors. This creates challenges for sectors and incurs extra cost, as bodies of knowledge gained in one sector are not easily accessible to others.

- There is a recognised **capability gap** across sectors and government, particularly in digital transformation and DSI design.
- A shared, evolving **body of knowledge**—covering technical, governance, and information management—would support future DSIs in transport, telecoms, agriculture, property, and other sectors.
- Use cases articulate the value in establishing fundamental technical and legal foundations, that can be iteratively built upon once in place.
- Capabilities evolve as use cases are delivered, building reusable patterns over time. These reusable patterns can become sector frameworks.

The Smart Data Strategy¹³ does not currently include the water sector. Government is planning to publish a cross-economy Smart Data Guidebook in 2027 which includes input from the energy sector but not from the water sector. It is important that where data sharing infrastructure initiatives are emerging in different sectors, that learning is captured and shared across sectors.

These steps summarise a development path for DSIs:

1. Initial design based on sector knowledge and early consultation (e.g. Energy DSI consulted NDTP¹⁴ and incorporated the NDTP technical approach after undertaking a feasibility study¹⁵) (e.g. Stream consulted extensively across water companies on user needs).
2. Illustrative use cases help define the boundaries and technical challenges.
3. Pilots and demonstrations validate architecture, trust frameworks, and governance.
4. Iterative refinement of capabilities, standards, and processes.
5. Scaling, informed by real-world usage, feedback, and interoperability needs.
6. Cross-sector evolution through shared use cases, aligned principles, and emerging national guidance.

The key ingredients to developing, scaling and connecting DSIs are **governance and collaboration**. It is ultimately people working together which will build cross-sector DSI.

“If we’re not member led we’re getting something wrong, a big part of developing Stream is ensuring everyone is aligned with the vision.”

Melissa Tallack, co-lead Stream

‘... a shared use case is viewed as essential to test interoperability between water and energy DSIs.’

References

¹³ [Smart Data Strategy – GOV.UK](#)

¹⁴ [Our collaborations – National Digital Twin Programme](#)

¹⁵ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/digital-spine-feasibility-study-exploring-a-data-sharing-infrastructure-for-the-energy-system>

Emerging DSIs in Energy and Water

continued

Stream values:

Openness

- Share our views and plans, and share knowledge as widely as possible;
- Solicit and listen to views from end users and stakeholders;
- Make appropriate outputs available under an open licence (e.g. CC-BY, OGL).

Expertise

- Bring our expertise to the discussion as individuals;
- Use our expertise to synthesise the views of others in constructive and forward-thinking proposals;
- Use good judgement to respect privacy and confidentiality.

Collaboration

- Support each other in discussion, in decisions and in delivery;
- Constructively hold each other to account on our commitments;
- Ensure all voices are heard and considered carefully.

There are lessons emerging from the development of the energy DSI and Stream:

- Sector based DSIs are emerging through the focus on specific use cases.
- An initial focus on specific use cases helps to guide technical and legal development of a DSI within one sector.
- Fostering cross-industry collaborative conversations in a pre-competitive space does require effort but it ultimately helps to deliver more value.
- The learning from initial use cases forms a dynamic body of knowledge.
- This dynamic body of knowledge can be translated into sector level frameworks to enable scaling. But at the moment there is no means for setting out cross-sector level frameworks.
- Avoid duplication – use open-source code bases such as NDTP¹⁶ resources where possible and applicable.
- Developing processes to publish multiple data products will enable multiple use cases and wide stakeholder participation. Focusing on trust and security through trust frameworks¹⁷ and shared data licensing is crucial. Scalable data licensing is a key part of DSI to enable the sharing of any type of data with the appropriate access controls.
- Over time, as standard processes are developed, a more comprehensive data sharing infrastructure naturally emerges, capable of handling diverse data types.
- Sector level frameworks need to consider interoperability with other sector level frameworks and to contribute to a national level approach to DSI.

The Energy Digitalisation Framework¹⁸ published on 23 March 2026, sets out DESNZ's expectations for interoperability in the energy sector applicable to GB. The framework referred to as the "Vision" sets out that, "Interoperability is not only the technical ability for systems to interface, but the full alignment of common processes and standards... the three areas of interoperability and the standardised approaches that industry must consider individually and collectively... are: trust framework interoperability, common accreditation processes, and consistent approaches to data standards, technical standards, and core technical components." The vision sets out that in developing the DSI and the consumer consent service, "interoperability between the frameworks must be treated as an essential design requirement going forward." It also says that NESO and the Retail Energy Code Company (RECCo) must be cognizant of "Interoperability between the GB energy sector and other sectors of the economy: This is expected to deliver significant additional value to consumers and the economy and should inform design decisions." The Digitalisation coordination function which is not yet established and due to be consulted on later in 2026 is expected to ensure interoperability and alignment with other sectors. Without a national level coordinating authority or equivalent coordination functions in other sectors, it is not clear how such a coordination function could ensure interoperability and alignment with other sectors. Energy leads digitalisation governance through the net zero imperative, and it needs comparable national level governance to interact with.

References

¹⁶ [Home - National Digital Twin Programme](#)

¹⁷ [Trust Frameworks – Icebreaker One](#)

¹⁸ [Energy digitalisation framework: a vision for a coordinated and connected energy system \(accessible webpage\) – GOV.UK](#)

GIG Recommendations

“The DSI has the prospective of transforming the energy sector by connecting data and organisation beyond the traditional boundaries to form a high-impact coalition, undertaking major challenges that is far beyond individual organisation, and bring whole-system benefits for the current and future energy companies, innovators and communities/customers.”

Li et al (2025)

Recommendations on enabling interoperability between sector DSIs

- We need more cross-sector use cases (e.g. energy and water, energy and transport, energy, water and transport etc), that are focused on joining up existing and emerging DSIs, to develop learnings to enable cross-sector data sharing. Only through trialling approaches will it become clear whether sector DSIs must become users of other sector DSIs or whether it is possible to create a cross-sector DSI. These cross-sector use cases must be obliged to share learnings with the wider community and other sector-based DSIs.
- We need cross-sector governance to support the development of cross-sector frameworks (which would be based on sector level frameworks and cross-sector use cases) – a mix of top down and bottom up.
- There is a strong need for cross-sector coordination, aligned frameworks, and better visibility of “who to talk to” in each sector. Enabling access to the “front door” of a sector-based DSI emerged as a key requirement. A people centred approach through regular forums for communication and discussion are vital to make progress.

GIG Recommendations

To overcome the persistent barriers to sharing data across sectors, coordinated action is required across: **Governance, Interoperability, and Guidance (GIG)**. At the centre of this approach is the creation of a **Data Sharing Infrastructure (DSI) Forum**, which becomes the convening space for communication, aligning standards, validating best practice, and supporting adoption across sectors. This report makes three GIG recommendations:

1. Governance: Establish a Clear, Hybrid, and Authoritative Framework

The UK needs a national data sharing infrastructure governance model that provides both clarity and practicality. This requires two complementary mechanisms:

- **A central coordinating authority providing both strategic and technical governance.** This coordinating authority would be responsible for setting strategic direction, resolving governance conflicts across sectors, and endorsing standards and best practice. This body ensures coherence and prevents fragmentation or capture. This level of strategic governance sets the vision for data sharing infrastructure and facilitates the join up of initiatives across government and industry through the Data Sharing Infrastructure Forum.
- **The Data Sharing Infrastructure Forum**, a cross-sector community of practitioners empowered to develop, test, and validate operational best practice and then communicate it to the wider data sharing community. The Forum provides input into the technical governance arm of the coordinating authority where architectural choices need to be made, facilitating integration and preventing vendor lock-in. The Forum translates best practice into practical implementation guidance which can be used across initiatives and sectors. If funded appropriately, the Forum could support active experimentation, for example, working on specific use cases requiring interoperability between sector DSIs. Working groups would be led by specialists and coordinated within the Forum. Forum advisory groups could be formed to support emergent sector DSIs.

GIG Recommendations

continued

‘The collaborative spirit of the DSWG could form the basis of a people-centred approach to developing cross-sector DSI.’

Using the language and approach initiated by DESNZ, Ofgem and NESO in the energy sector, DSIT could set out a vision for connecting up sector based DSIs. The collaborative spirit of the DSWG could form the basis of a people-centred approach to developing cross-sector DSI by providing the seeds of a data sharing infrastructure forum.

2. Interoperability: Create Shared Foundations and Standards for Cross-sector Data Sharing

- Data interoperability: A technical authority should be established within the Coordinating Authority (Recommendation 1) to facilitate and co-ordinate the interoperability approach taken across the economy and by all departments, providing benefits to all sector DSIs. In support of semantic interoperability: the technical authority should support the use and extension of a chosen Foundation Data Model building on UK expertise and recognising existing work in this space such as that of NDTP¹⁹, 4DSIG²⁰ and Project CONCRETE²¹. This is aligned with the European Interoperability Framework Recommendation 31²²: “Put in place an information management strategy at the highest possible level to avoid fragmentation and duplication. Management of metadata, master data and reference data should be prioritised.”
- Clear data flows with specified information requirements are essential to data interoperability. This supports enabling high quality data, data governance, and data provenance, to ensure information is fit for the required purposes. Organisations must adopt a methodology and process to articulate and organise use cases, capture what information is needed, for what purpose, in what location, for how long, and how that information is to be managed as a data flow. This is a fundamental part of future standards and is a prerequisite to secure information interoperability.
- Data sharing practitioners should contribute to the development of:
 - minimum viable standards for data sharing supporting data quality and stewardship.
 - legal building blocks, including reusable data sharing agreements and liability frameworks.
- Emerging DSIs need to investigate options for legal interoperability and shared trust frameworks.

3. Guidance: Provide Clear, Practical, and Authoritative Materials to Reduce Complexity and duplication

For organisations to share data confidently and responsibly, they need accessible, consistent, and actionable guidance which applies across sectors. Interoperability guidance should be a key part of this which also enables consistency across different aspects of the guidance. The DSI Forum should test, curate and publish a structured and evolving library of authoritative materials, including and not limited to:

- good-practice checklists.
- templated data sharing agreements.
- risk-based decision frameworks.
- minimum data quality and stewardship standards.
- ontology guidance.
- practical definitions and models of what constitutes a Data Sharing Infrastructure.

These materials should be openly available, regularly updated, and endorsed by the central coordinating authority. Importantly, they should be accompanied by training materials and capability-building programmes to strengthen the UK’s data sharing culture.

References

19 [Home – National Digital Twin Programme](#)

20 4D Special Interest Group chaired by Dame Wendy Hall.

21 Project CONCRETE, under development in the Ministry of Defence (unclassified), is developing an open, user-centric, sector-agnostic blueprint for secure digital collaboration and interoperability in support of minimal national digital standards.

22 <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/lopeu-monitoring/3-interoperability-layers#3.5>

GIG Recommendations and Conclusion

Figure 3

A Coordinating Authority provides strategic and technical governance. A Data Sharing Infrastructure Forum provides best practice guidance to support interoperability across sector data sharing infrastructures.

Conclusion

The UK's current data sharing environment is fragmented, uncertain, and vulnerable to emerging market power dynamics. Without decisive action, organisations will continue to face barriers that limit innovation and undermine public trust. Establishing a **Data Sharing Infrastructure Forum**, supported by a central coordinating authority, provides the people-centred approach to enabling sector-agnostic interoperability.

By taking this approach, the UK can build data sharing infrastructure that is trusted, interoperable, pro-competitive, and aligned with the public interest, unlocking the full value of data across sectors and ensuring long-term digital resilience.

Annex 1: Energy and Water DSIs

Annex 1: Sharing data across energy and water data sharing infrastructures

NESO is developing the **Energy Data Sharing Infrastructure (Energy DSI)**²³ and Stream is developing the **Water Data Sharing Infrastructure (Water DSI)**²⁴. Further information regarding these sector based data sharing infrastructures can be found on their websites. A workshop was held to explore points of alignment across the two sector DSIs and to explore how cross-sector use cases between energy and water could be supported.

The following key points emerged as observations from the discussion but do not represent the formal position of NESO or Stream:

1. Standards and Interoperability

- Both sectors rely on **sector defined standards**; neither DSI chooses standards itself.
- An early standard being prioritised is the **Common Information Model (CIM)** in electricity and work is underway for a CIM in gas.
- Water has fewer established standards and often must decide between multiple existing standards or create new ones. Participants take a collaborative approach to agreeing data publication standards so that data can be more easily joined within and across sectors. The preference is to adopt and align with existing standards to maximise interoperability.
- Both sectors use **schema assurance / conformity checking**. Stream applies a formal scoring/feedback loop to improve data quality over time. Energy DSI is considering the scoring approach for future development.
- Stream has introduced a dataset validation tool to automatically compare Stream published datasets against agreed documentation to ensure that data is fit for use.
- A shared challenge is **identifying which standard applies** when many exist.

2. Consumer Data

- The Consumer Consent Service is being developed by the Retail Energy Code Company (RECCo) and alignment is being worked through for inclusion in the Energy DSI, but not immediately.
- The Stream DSI is **open to including consumer data**, but its inclusion depends entirely on use case needs and on avoiding duplication of existing services.
- Consumer data introduces complex issues around **consent**, which is recognised as a major technical and legal challenge in both sectors.

3. Data Triage Processes

- Energy sees triage as an **internal business process** that precedes use of the DSI.
- Stream operates a two-stage process with a joint risk assessment conducted first across participants (to harmonise risk appetite and prioritisation) followed by an **internal company triage**.
- The water sector's collective triage process helps align different risk appetites and interpretations across companies.
- The energy DSI does not replicate ENA led triage activities but could **initiate requests** that feed into them.

4. Stakeholders

Energy:

- Current users: almost all regulated gas and electricity transmission and distribution networks. By April 2028, it will be expected to be used by all regulated gas and electricity transmission and distribution networks.
- From April 2028: open participation for all interested organisations (eg local authorities, universities).
- Ofgem and DESNZ are being onboarded as participants.

Water:

- Current publishers: regulated water companies in Great Britain (including Scotland and Wales).
- Open to all water companies in UK including Northern Ireland.
- Broader user ecosystem includes government bodies, regulators, trade bodies,

References

- [23 Data Sharing Infrastructure \(DSI\) | National Energy System Operator](#)
- [24 Stream - Portal](#)

Annex 1: Energy and Water DSIs

continued

private enterprises, academia, citizen science groups, campaigners, and the supply chain (via trade bodies). Any participant operating in the water sector who would like to use Stream to access or supply data relevant to water sector data eg citizen science data.

Shared Need:

- A future requirement is to identify “**front doors**” in other sectors beyond energy and water to facilitate cross-sector engagement more easily.

5. Funding Models

- Energy DSI benefits from **regulator-approved funding**, making participation costs recoverable as part of regulated business plans. NESO covers upfront costs of DSI through its regulated business plan.
- Stream relies on **voluntary member subscriptions from water companies** plus innovation funding, which creates risks around financial sustainability.
- The water sector would benefit from a similar regulated funding model, as implemented in energy.
- Participation in both sectors may generate variable costs depending on the complexity of each participant's deployment.
- Energy sector participants in the energy DSI would need to cover the costs of a data preparation node.
- The licences needed to publish data to Stream are covered in the Stream membership cost.

6. Use Case Discussion: Energy–Water Operational Risk Use Case

A shared use case was used to explore interoperability between the DSIs:

Scenario:

- Water companies need to understand dynamic energy supply fluctuations that could disrupt asset operation and lead to service interruptions and impacts such as pollution events.
- Energy networks could benefit from knowing which water assets are functionally “critical” (even if small) to prioritise attention during outages or dips.

Data exchange:

- Water would supply **static asset information**.
- Energy would supply **dynamic operational data**.
- Both sectors could access data products via each other's DSIs, provided membership, authentication, and licences are aligned.
- Both sectors need to investigate options for legal interoperability and shared trust frameworks.

7. Governance and Licensing

- Both DSIs operate layered governance:
 - **Membership / participation agreements**
 - **Use case specific arrangements**
 - **Licensing models governing permitted use**
- Water is currently developing a **master framework approach with use case specific terms**.
- Energy is designing around **a set of standard licences with bespoke options**, to enable clarity and consistency.
- Cross-sector collaboration requires:
 - alignment between participation agreements,
 - interoperability of licence types, and
 - clarity about who governs joint use cases.

8. Security and Trust

- A challenge for Energy DSI is **risk ownership** across a federated architecture where participants deploy their own nodes in diverse cloud environments and differing approaches to 'bring your own device' models for technical connectivity.

Annex 1: Energy and Water DSIs

continued

- Government bodies require extremely **specific definitions of risk** before offering guidance.
- Stream faces similar challenges and noted the value of shared learning.
- Both sectors recognise the need to:
 - understand where there is **equivalence between the DSIs** so that if an organisation is accredited in one DSI, it can also gain entry to the other DSI.
 - align authentication and authorisation mechanisms,
 - clarify escalation paths for security breaches.

9. Opportunities for Cross-sector Coordination

- Interoperable legal frameworks and licence models.
- Joint guidance on governance, trust, and security.
- A **supported cross-sector forum** to enable DSIs in different sectors to stay aligned enough to interoperate without friction rather than to diverge.
- Building on energy's technical work (eg NDTP codebase), enabling other sectors to start further ahead.
- Shared involvement in national efforts like the **smart data scheme guidebook** to ensure consistency.

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